

E-RIHS

EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

E-RIHS IP

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science IMPLEMENTATION Phase

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02 | TYPE OF ACTION: CSA | GA n. 101079148

D5.5 E-RIHS ERIC Access Policy: Approach and Advancement

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ABSTRACT

This report focuses on the working strategy that is being set to update the access policy for E-RIHS. To ensure a comprehensive document, we believe it is crucial to build upon the foundation established during the preparatory phase of E-RIHS PP. This existing document encompasses years of reflection and practical experience, gained through previous European Integrating Activities such as IPERION CH (H2020) and CHARISMA (FP7) and IPERION HS (Horizon Europe). Furthermore, it has undergone review by the E-RIHS platform coordinators.

The User Strategy aims to be forward-looking, taking into account both current and potential future users. This ongoing work is treated in parallel tasks that will feed into the developments of this task. It will outline the necessary processes for gathering information to assess the needs of existing and prospective users. Additionally, the strategy will highlight the ways in which this information can be utilized within E-RIHS decision-making processes. The development of the strategy will closely align with parallel tasks related to users in other E-RIHS IP work packages.

By leveraging the existing foundation and incorporating insights from various stakeholders, the updated access policy will address the evolving needs of users and ensure effective decision-making within the E-RIHS framework.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Project number	101079148	Acronym	E-RIHS IP
Full title	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Implementation Phase		
Project url	www.e-rihs.eu		
Document url			
EU Project Officer	Emiliano CAROZZA		

Deliverable	Number	D5.5	Title	E-RIHS ERIC Access Policy: Approach and Advancement
Work Package	Number	5	Title	Access and Digital services of E-RIHS

Deliverable nature	Report		
Dissemination level	☒ Public ☐ Confidential ☐ Restricted		
Contractual delivery date	(31/07/2023)		
Actual delivery date	(29/09/2023)		
Status	Version 3	☒ Draft ☐ Final	

Authors (Partner)	MCC-FSP	
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Total number of pages	19
Keywords	Access policy, platforms

Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. no.	Author	Change
28/07/2023	1	Victor Etgens	Initial version
29/09/23	2	Victor Etgens	1 st revision
30/09/23	3	Vania Virgili	Final revision

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Table 1: Non-exhaustive list of colleagues who were identified to participate in the work to be done

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2 ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Expansion
CCSI	Cultural and Creative Sectors and Industries
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CON	Communication Officers Network
CSA	Cooperative and Support Action
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DISSCO	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
DORA	Declaration on Research Assessment
EGI-ACE	EGI Advanced Computing for EOSC
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science

EHRI	European Holocaust Research Infrastructure
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
HS	Heritage Science
iCNN	Interim Committee of National Nodes
iGA	Interim General Assembly
OPERAS	European Research infrastructure for open scholarly communication in SSH
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RI	Research Infrastructure(s)
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound

3 INTRODUCING SOME DEFINITIONS

Users:

- Users can be individuals and group centres, industry or other private and public institutions involved in Heritage Science. They are actors in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems or in project management.
- Teams of users can include researchers, technical staff and students undertaking research in their studies framework. According to its scientific strategy, E-RIHS will encourage applications from users' teams with a strong interdisciplinary character.

Types of eligible objects:

- Research on cultural heritage, objects, monuments or sites belonging to the public domain.
- E-RIHS can accept projects involving private elements (collection, object, sample or monument), if:
 - the item is listed as an international, national or regional interest and is accessible and reusable to the public;
 - the object belongs to an individual but remains in a public institution. In the working groups different intellectual property management scenarios may be considered to the final document, meaning objects in the public domain, others managed and owned by public institutions and others managed by public institutions and owned by the creators or third parties;
 - the object is a private property, but it is an essential element of a corpus of objects belonging to the public domain.

Access modes:

- based on excellence for physical platforms (FIXLAB, MOLAB, ARCHLAB);
- a wide access to digital activities on E-RIHS DIGILAB;
- a limited commercial access (to be defined, according to the global strategies of E-RIHS).

Access cost:

Main principles:

- Free access should be promoted. If this is not the case, the costs should be bounded to:
 - No for-profit and limited overheads;
 - If applicable, internal access costs should be offered through E-RIHS;
 - Costs should be comprehensively described via a cost policy in the catalogue before proposals are submitted;
 - Access providers are solely responsible for billing and following up on payments.
- Travel and accommodation costs (including MOLAB) are borne by the users by default, but they can apply to a travel grant.
- E-RIHS is not liable for the transportation and/or insurance costs of the objects.

4 INVENTORY OF EXISTING DOCUMENTS

4.1 Introduction

As already stated, it is necessary to consider as a starting point two major documents: the access policy documents of IPERION HS and E-RIHS PP.

Moreover, it is necessary to integrate the experience acquired by the facility coordinators of the IPERION HS program that is *currently* running. It is also necessary to integrate the common points applied for the four access platforms (FIXLAB, MOLAB, ARCHLAB and DIGILAB) and to consider their differences in terms of the access policy into the final document. Table I, describes some non-exhaustive topics that require an update for the final deliverable.

Table 2: Questions requiring discussion, clarification or improvement in the access policy

Points that are still requiring refinement	To be discussed priority with
Define more precisely the feasibility and scientific and technical relevance checks performed by the providers	FIXLAB, MOLAB, ARCHLAB
Refine eligibility criteria, especially for non-EU users, private actors and “national accesses.”	FIXLAB, MOLAB, ARCHLAB
Projects associating different platforms (Wide access)	FIXLAB, MOLAB, ARCHLAB, DIGILAB
Define procedures for exploratory projects	FIXLAB, MOLAB, ARCHLAB
Define the modality for remote access in the access policy	FIXLAB
Discuss “Fast Track” access modalities for ARCHLAB (if only one provider is requested + additional conditions?)	FIXLAB, MOLAB, ARCHLAB
Platform pricing/economic model (business plan)	FIXLAB, MOLAB
Discuss potential commercial/market access procedures.	FIXLAB, MOLAB, ARCHLAB, DIGILAB
Define procedures and terms for long-term projects	FIXLAB, MOLAB, ARCHLAB, DIGILAB

* This task overlaps with catalogue of services and updated application form. A homogenization must to be done latter.

4.2 Document IPERION HS referring on Access Policy

The European project IPERION HS provides Trans-National Access but in many aspects this is the real test for the E-RIHS ERIC Access Policy. Thanks to the funding of the European Commission under the Grant Agreement n° 871034, IPERION HS provides a free charge access for the users. Travelling and accommodations costs are based by the providers in compliance with their national or local rules.

Access refers to the legitimated and authorised physical, remote and virtual admission to the interaction with IPERION HS services offered. Such access is granted amongst others to machine

time, computing resources, software, data, communication services data, sample preparation, archives, collections, the set-up, execution and dismantling of experiments, expert support and analytical services.

IPERION HS selects projects in the excellence-driven access mode. This process includes an eligibility evaluation by the physical platforms and a feasibility assessment performed by the selected access providers prior to the Peer Review Panel (PRP) evaluation. Independent experts compose this PRP across the Heritage Science disciplines. Integrated weighted criteria include - scientific excellence (35%); assessment of the state of the art of the topic and advancements in the field (25%) valorisation and dissemination plan (20%) expertise of User Group (15%) and potential impact (5%). Access is provided under the condition that the user group leader and the majority of the group users work in an EU or associated country other than the countries where the installations are located. Access for groups with a majority of users working outside EU is limited to 20% of the total amount of units of access. Legal restrictions or technical limits may apply on a case-by-case basis.

4.3 Document E-RIHS PP referring on Access Policy

The D.5.1 User strategy and access policies of E-RIHS PP, led by Claire Pacheco has described the bases of the E-RIHS access policies for E-RIHS ERIC deliver access through its four platforms: “E-RIHS ARCHLAB”, “E-RIHS DIGILAB”, “E-RIHS FIXLAB” and “E-RIHS MOLAB”. Such document is targeted to bring the bases to enable users’ access to its physical and virtual research facilities.

This deliverable herein can be separated in two main parts serving different purposes.

The first part, “E-RIHS Access Policy”, is designed to provide answers to a broad audience about the principles that will drive access in E-RIHS. Definitions and explanations of key terms, core values and different modes and types of access by E-RIHS are also included in this first part.

The second part of the document, “E-RIHS Access Procedures”, defines the procedures, the eligibility criteria, and typical proposed project access that may be granted. This part is less detailed than the former one, mostly as it is heavily dependent on the ongoing work on governance, legal, financial, and managerial aspects of E-RIHS. However, it still provides a solid foundation for the access policy to be further detailed according to the final E-RIHS global strategy.

The E-RIHS access policy and subsequent access procedures have been designed in accordance with the European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures 2016 [2] and taken into account the ESFRI recommendations on the E-RIHS Preparatory Phase (accepted) proposal for inclusion into the 2016 roadmap [5] as well as important and further modifications for E-RIHS in 2021.

Scientific excellence has been until now been the main core of the access policy, with a peer reviewing process conducted by external experts. The selected platforms of projects make a verification about the overall feasibility of each submitted research proposal.

This document is used as a formal base to sediment the E-RIHS access policy, updated and continually improved upon by the experience gathered in IPERION HS e, as from many rounds of discussions with the access providers and the user’s community.

4.4 Key Messages

Until now, the only access mode has been based on scientific excellence for the three physical platforms. Concerning DIGILAB, a specific task is devoted to the implementation plan in E-RIHS IP. We will create a continuous exchange with leaders of this task, to ensure the best access policy for DIGILAB, that fully depends on the planned platform ambition. A possible idea is that a wide access mode should be taken for many digital activities in E-RIHS DIGILAB.

The involvement of the interim Committee of National Coordinators (iCNC) is a starting point to the preparation of the E-RIHS access policy. Concerning DIGILAB, a dedicated task is devoted to it and it is important to integrate their conclusions on the final document. The first proposition is feedback on the already existing documents. The second part considers adjustments in the present document "The main principles of the access policy" can serve as very first version for the discussions that will come.

It will then be necessary to identify the names of providers to participate at the meetings that are to be organized to work on the document based on their representation of a community and/or service type within an E-RIHS platform. This document also requests consensus by the E-RIHS interim General Assembly (iGA).

5 WORK PLANNING

The main principles for the access procedure are based in a central European hub that centralizes all requests developed by national equivalents for the E-RIHS national access.

A "Helpdesk" assistance service helps to advise and optimize the submission of projects, in addition to local contacts.

Submission of projects following calls on fixed dates or according to a continuous flux. Concerning that point, it is necessary to decide if ARCHLAB and DIGILAB demands cannot be more flexible. Also, it will be very important to propose issues about fast-track access for urgent projects. This is planned to be done in the next coming meeting. Another important question is the definition of the place attributed to commercial/market access.

One single request may concern several access providers. The consortium is building an exploitation strategy for services, licensing, spin-off creation, joint ventures, etc. ensuring the success and sustainability of E-RIHS ERIC as an innovator and a leader in the global Heritage Science landscape.

Within E-RIHS IP exploitation means:

1. Elaborate a strategy for exploiting innovation generated in the E-RIHS ecosystem in view of the future ERIC;
2. Maximize the impact of E-RIHS IP activities on the current and future E-RIHS community of users and access providers;
3. Maximize the impact of E-RIHS IP activities on other RIs and on the cultural and creative sectors.

5.1 Work still to be done: Sharing at European level

Currently, we have updated the document that serves as a basis for the work in E-RIHS, based on the E-RIHS PP D.5.1 User Strategy and Access Policies and the work being conducted in IPERION HS. This update was conducted in collaboration with key providers, including discussions with the responsible individuals from FIXLAB, MOLAB, and ARCHLAB of IPERION HS, all of whom are involved in E-RIHS IP.

Our next step is to organize large meetings with access providers from all E-RIHS ERIC partners. The main aim of these meetings will be to work collaboratively on the document's evolution in accordance with the E-RIHS IP version. Additionally, it will be crucial to address important open questions, some of which are outlined in Table I, such as the differentiation between national access and transnational access policies.

It is highly valuable to draw from the experience of IPERION HS in terms of the access policy, as well as lessons learnt from the feedback therein regarding the challenges and issues encountered. This will aid us in enhancing the E-RIHS IP document. The subsequent step involves engaging in discussions with the wider community, which will play a vital role in shaping the final quality of the document. Please, refer to the Gantt chart in the next section for an overview of our planned activities.

5.2 Gantt Chart for E-RIHS ERIC Access Policy

Gantt Chart for -RIHS ERIC Access Policy

6 THE MAIN PRINCIPLES OF THE ACCESS POLICY

This provisory text needs to be discussed, worked with national nodes coordinators, and platform coordinators.

6.1 Access Mode

Access to the four E-RIHS platforms will be provided according to different modes: an **Excellence-driven access mode** for the physical platforms (E-RIHS ARCHLAB, E-RIHS FIXLAB and E-RIHS MOLAB), a **Wide access** mode for two or more digital activities platforms on E-RIHS DIGILAB, once again in agreement with the specific task dedicated to DIGILAB. The **Market-driven access mode** in accordance with the planning of E-RIHS ERIC commercial activities that may also be considered, according to the global ERIHS strategies to be developed by the project.

This part will be developed with explicit real examples from the catalogue of services in the following meetings.

Excellence-driven access is exclusively dependent on scientific excellence, the quality of an application evaluated through a peer-reviewing process conducted by external experts. The feasibility of the research proposal is assessed by the facility Local Technical Committee (LTC).

Wide access / digital access enables to reach scientific data and digital services provided by E-RIHS DIGILAB to users wherever they are based and following the FAIR and Open Access principles: “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

Market-Driven access is defined through a commercial contract between the user and the provider in accordance with the E-RIHS ERIC rules of procedures for commercial activities, to be further elaborated in the future. Because of the statutory nature of E-RIHS ERIC, this access mode will remain limited both in volume and in numbers, if the E-RIHS General Assembly allows market-driven accesses.

Excellence-driven access (E-RIHS ARCHLAB, E-RIHS FIXLAB and E-RIHS MOLAB) E-RIHS will only grant access to scientific projects falling within the E-RIHS scope, as described in its Scientific Strategy. Access is free of charge and not restricted to members or observers of E-RIHS ERIC. Scientists from E-RIHS partner institutions will not be granted unfair advantages in the scientific selection process or in the attribution of travel and accommodation grants. However, E-RIHS ERIC may grant practical advantages to its members at some point during the access process in respect to non-member. This question needs also to be clarify with providers and the community. Deliverable D5.1 E-RIHS PP – GA n. 739503 9 E-RIHS ERIC will enable multi-platforms and long-term projects. Long-term projects will allow users to access multiple facilities in a time span of several years. In order to carry out long-term projects, users will have to apply for an E-RIHS certificate through the normal access selection procedure that are still to be discusses and clarified. The final procedures still to be discussed in more details. The E-RIHS PRP will then perform an extensive evaluation of the project during the first call, and regular assessments will be carried out along the duration of the long-term projects. E-RIHS national coordinators may announce yearly the ratio of long-term projects of their Access providers to the E-RIHS Head Office.

E-RIHS users will only undertake research concerning publicly owned cultural and scientific collections, artefacts, objects, samples, monuments or sites. However, E-RIHS can accept projects involving privately owned items (i.e. collection, artefact, object, sample or monument), when:

- the item is listed as being of relevance at the international, national or regional level and is accessible to the public; or,
- the item is privately owned but deposited in a public institution; or,
- the item is privately owned but it is an essential element of a publicly-owned corpus of items.

Digital access (E-RIHS DIGILAB) E-RIHS supports an Open Access policy to data and digital services. However, access limitations may be necessary for copyright reasons, personal and privacy-sensitive

data protection, and to protect legitimate Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). E-RIHS abides by the DARIAH Heritage Data Re-Use Charter [9]. All scientific data will be stored and curated at “local” repositories under the responsibility of a partner or a cooperating institution, with possible exceptions for a small number of reference datasets, such as vocabularies, reference tables, manuals, etc. which may be stored with the E-RIHS DIGILAB Catalogue to facilitate searches or to support the DIGILAB use. E-RIHS partners provide data access at the conditions specified below and share the metadata for their datasets to the E-RIHS DIGILAB Catalogue according to a common data model. Access to tools and services is provided through the main portal of E-RIHS DIGILAB. E-RIHS DIGILAB will favour free and open-source digital tools and services. However, there could also be some paid tools and services if they provide a significant added value to the platform, and assuming that they comply with the E-RIHS ERIC ethics and values and with the limits on commercial activities laid down by the ERIC regulation. Access to data is provided through the E-RIHS DIGILAB Catalogue, which enables searching the metadata and finding datasets stored in “local” repositories. The E-RIHS DIGILAB Authentication, Identification and Authorization System will provide a federated identity system to all participating data managers and to all the categories of users. User access will be regulated with different level of privileges, with a system of Registered Users Datasets. Conditions for data re-use must be specified in each dataset metadata. Such conditions may refer to general licensing schemes (e.g. Creative Commons) or to specific re-use conditions established by the data owner/depositor as well as by legal constraints, e.g. a non-transferable use license. A “re-use document” summarizing legal re-use constraints should be available in each participating repository and referenced in each dataset.

6.2 E-RIHS Access procedure

Access to E-RIHS platforms could be provided according to the three different modes as aforementioned: an Excellence-driven access mode for the three physical platforms (E-RIHS ARCHLAB, E-RIHS FIXLAB and E-RIHS MOLAB). A wide access mode for digital activities on E-RIHS DIGILAB. Finally, a Market-driven access mode, in accordance with the provisions for E-RIHS ERIC commercial activities, integrating the restrictions imposed on commercial activities by the ERIC regulation. Important information can be found in [10].

Only the first two first modes are described here. Access to E-RIHS platforms rely on in-kind contributions from E-RIHS partners. This means that the access platforms will provide access to answer research questions concerning to the entire scope of Heritage Science as long as they stay within the legal and statutory providers boundaries. Potential users may contact the E-RIHS Helpdesk. This Helpdesk will inform the users on the admissibility of their project and assist them in the preparation of their proposal. The key feature of this preliminary support will be to offer a contact with the potential access providers to facilitate the preparation of proposals for access. A prospective user will be able to contact the E-RIHS helpdesk in order to be redirected to the relevant E-RIHS partners that may help them direct their research questions. For example, in the case of synchrotron facilities, a user will be encouraged to contact a relevant beam line scientist and ask any necessary question therein.

A single entry point

A single digital entry point for access to the four platforms will be managed by the Central Hub. E-RIHS will set up a Help Desk which will intervene in the various steps of proposal submission,

assisting users in the proposal compilation and directing them to the most appropriate platform/facility.

Excellence-driven access (E-RIHS ARCHLAB, E-RIHS FIXLAB and E-RIHS MOLAB)

E-RIHS Users will typically request access to an E-RIHS facility by submitting a proposal that involves researchers or Heritage Stakeholders from various fields and institutions, although single users can also apply. In both cases, one person, the user group leader, will be responsible for the administrative contact with E-RIHS. User Group Leaders will be requested to fill out a specific application form to apply for E-RIHS access. Applications may be submitted in reply to calls regularly issued by E-RIHS, or any open calls for some resources. Each call will outline a selection of providers offering access. If the User Group assumes that several providers are granting comparable accesses, the Group Leader is free to select one or more options that are the most appropriate to their project and, if applicable, provide the Central Hub with an order of preference.

Users will be encouraged to use the CCO Public domain mark by default. However, they will also be given the choice to select one of the Creative Commons licenses. This suite of licenses offers 6 possibilities that can accommodate most of the users' needs while abiding by the E-RIHS values. This part of the application will also lay down the rules on the transfer of the project data to E-RIHS DIGILAB (when applicable). Each Excellence-driven access proposal will be evaluated following the procedure as schematized in the flowchart below. This procedure will consist in an administrative eligibility check of the proposal by the Central Hub (not shown in the diagram) and a feasibility assessment of the proposal followed by a scientific evaluation. The latter steps respectively involve a Local Technical Committee (LTC) and a Peer Review Panel (PRP), as explained below. These steps are executed as follows:

Step 0: Administrative eligibility of the proposal by the Central Hub

The Central Hub confirms that the eligibility criteria access are met. It can reject proposals at this point if science is not the core motivation of the proposal. A non-eligible proposal would be, for example, a project where the "scientific content" is only related to concealing an authentication request. This step is preliminary to evaluate and for the sake of clarity, it is not shown in the chart.

Step 1: Feasibility of the proposal

The feasibility assessment of a proposal is carried out at the provider level by a Local Technical Committee (LTC) according to a common predefined criteria. This committee can take several forms and its composition may vary according to the nature of the proposal:

- personnel in charge of the access for archives, mobile and fixed instruments;
- existing local help desks for large-scale instruments;
- LTC members cannot evaluate proposals in which they have a conflict of interest.

The overall assessment feasibility of a proposal will result in a Yes/No report by the LTC, followed by detailed comments explaining their decision. This decision can be eliminatory if the technique is not appropriate to answer the research questions, the archives do not exist or are not accessible, or any other reason that makes the proposal irrelevant. In such a case, the Central Hub will reject the proposal as it is upon recommendation by the LTC, without sending it to the PRP for the scientific evaluation. These analyses will be used to justify the refusal to the User Group Leader. The provider

can also suggest another provider for technical reasons or skills and know-how. A complement of the proposed study with other techniques can also be recommended at this step. If a long-term project needs several accesses, the proposal must justify such a request. If the project requires different types of instruments or archives for an access that would be granted by several providers, each concerned provider will perform an overall feasibility local assessment.

Step 2: Scientific evaluation

The Scientific Evaluation access proposals for all types of physical access will be carried out by a unique multi-disciplinary international Peer Review Panel (PRP). A pool of renown international experts, covering a wide range of knowledge and expertise within the field of Heritage Science will be nominated by E-RIHS for the review of proposals. Due to the very large number of proposals, the E-RIHS PRP will be organized in several groups, so that each proposal is not evaluated by the entire pool of experts. A core Peer Review Panel will evaluate the general scientific excellence of the projects, while subgroups will evaluate a platform or a subgroup specific criteria. This must to be discussed and organized in the next meetings.

Peer Reviewers will be selected among the pool of referees, avoiding any conflict of interest. The core Peer Review Panel members will fill out a predefined selection grid according to the general selection criteria to be validated by the general assembly. Each platform or platform subgroup will establish their platform specific criteria, which might be adapted to the exploratory or long-term nature of the projects, to the relevant heritage conservation criteria, and to the adequacy of the requested technique.

The “evaluation criteria” of the E-RIHS Access meeting held at the C2RMF in Paris on 22nd October 2019 suggested the following general selection criteria: the relevance of the project to Heritage Science, as well as the general scientific excellence, the ethics of the project, the data management plan and the planned dissemination activities.

Each platform or sub-group of platforms can also define a sub-criteria provided that they are compatible with the general evaluation criteria. The following are tentative breakdowns of scientific excellence, cross-disciplinary and ethics:

Scientific excellence:

- Originality / news value
- State of art
- Previous results, legacy, former publications
- Potential scientific expansion of the project
- Excellence of the proposal

Cross-disciplinary:

- Proposal
- Team background

Ethical criteria:

- Assessment
- Engagement (society)

Some criteria can only be assessed by reviewers with a direct knowledge of the proposal precise field and of the techniques required. They include:

- The literature review assessment

- The necessity to use this particular technique
- The Industrial outreach and impact (broadly speaking)
- The early contacts with the helpdesk or the potential providers (if applicable)

Step 3: Ranking of proposals

The final assessment and ranking are given by the PRP. Proposals are ranked from the highest mark to the lowest. The Central Hub then grants the access to the highest scoring projects as long as the requested access slot is available. If not, users can be redirected by the Central Hub to their second choice, and the evaluation process is restarted. Users can choose to resubmit for the next call in case of a fixed timetable.

Step 4: Final step

The Central Hub officially announces to the providers whether the proposals in which they were requested are accepted or not, but it does not plan the runs. Providers then perform final safety checks according to their own legal and internal regulations. These regulations are to be available online and will be compiled and explained by E-RIHS and helpdesk where necessary. If a proposal is accepted for access, the User Group Leader will be invited by the Central Hub to timely contact the provider to schedule and organize the access. If the proposal is not accepted, the User Group Leader will receive a justification by the Central Hub. Following any access, Users Group Leaders are required to fill out and return a satisfaction survey to the Central Hub, and to formally communicate any related publication or dissemination action that they may undertake. Users are also required to duly acknowledge the role of E-RIHS in the access provision.

E-RIHS access: proposal flowchart

Excellence driven access mode specific cases

- E-RIHS FIXLAB remote access

Some E-RIHS FIXLAB providers can make analysis on samples that can be sent by post-mail and the presence of the users is not compulsory. The platforms and laboratories that can provide E-RIHS FIXLAB remote access will be identified and the user group should explicitly ask for such an access. The proposal flowchart and the selection procedure remain the same as for any E-RIHS FIXLAB access.

- E-RIHS ARCHLAB access **(to be further discussed and defined with the platform coordinator)**

For E-RIHS ARCHLAB procedure, a proposal may go through a faster procedure, the evaluation being done by the PRP when the proposal arises.

- E-RIHS MOLAB access **(to be further discussed and defined with the platform coordinator)**

Wide access (E-RIHS DIGILAB)

User access regulation

User access is regulated as follows:

- Anonymous E-RIHS DIGILAB users may only access the Catalogue and Open Access datasets;
- Registered users can access Open Access Datasets, Open Access to Registered Users Datasets and Datasets with Restricted-Access Data with the exclusion of the restricted-access data.

The procedures to obtain special access permissions to restricted data or dataset may vary, but they will be explained to users trying to access them. The E-RIHS DIGILAB Authentication, Identification and Authorization System provides a federated identity system to all participating data managers and to all the categories of users. Data re-use Conditions for data re-use must be specified in each dataset metadata. Such conditions may refer to general licensing schemes (e.g. Creative Commons) or to specific re-use conditions established by the data owner/depositor as well as by legal constraints, e.g. a non-transferable use license. A “re-use document” summarizing legal re-use constraints should be available in each participating repository and referenced in each dataset. Access and use of digital tools and services E-RIHS will provide a number of digital services through its E-RIHS DIGILAB. Such services include, for example, visualization tools, data processing, statistical tools, data mining and so on. Some of these services will need to store data, and some will not. This distinction will have an impact on the accessibility of E-RIHS DIGILAB services:

- Services not requiring data storage will be available to anonymous and registered users with a simplified procedure related to the service such as making the results available for instantaneous download or sending the processed results by email.
- Services that need data storage will only be available to registered users. The detailed policy on the access to such services will be elaborated and updated at the level of E-RIHS ERIC. E-RIHS DIGILAB will favour free and open source digital tools and services. However, there could also be some paid tools and services if they provide a significant added value to the platform, and provided that they comply with the E-RIHS ERIC ethics and values and with the limits on commercial activities laid down by the ERIC regulation.

Market-driven access. It is currently being considered and evaluated as a way to provide an alternative funding mechanism to support access and ensure the sustainability of the research infrastructure. Further considerations and discussions are needed to develop the platform’s pricing and economic model, as also part of the revised E-RIHS Business Plan.

7 REFERENCES

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